

Teachers' Classroom Management Practices and Learners' Behavior

Princess Ivy B. Jayme¹, Rosalinda C. Tantiado²

¹Southern de Oro Philippines College, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

²DepEd-Cagayan de Oro City Division, Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

ABSTRACT: Proper classroom management is essential for shaping learners' behavior and creating an encouraging environment for learning. This study sought to evaluate the behavior of learners as well as the level of classroom management practices used by teachers in terms of planning, classroom instruction, and evaluation. This study also sought to evaluate the strong correlation between learners' behavior and teachers' classroom management practices. The research used a descriptive correlational design to examine the relationship between these variables. The respondents were 102 elementary teachers from Manolo Fortich District IV, Division of Bukidnon, SY 2024-2025 and were selected through purposive universal sampling. Data were collected using a modified survey questionnaire, which included the Classroom Management Scale (CMS) and the Classroom Behavior Rating Scale. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe the levels of classroom management practices and learners' behavior, while the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient tested the relationship between them. Findings showed that classroom instruction was a very highly evident aspect of teachers' classroom management practices while learners' behavior found to be generally positive. Overall, classroom management practices used by teachers have significant positive correlation with learners' behavior. It can be inferred that when teachers demonstrate effective classroom management practices learners behave well. Thus, by setting clear expectations and promoting school standards, school heads, teachers and parents may promote constructive behavior among learners.

KEYWORDS: classroom instruction, classroom management, learners' behaviour.

I. INTRODUCTION

An effective classroom environment provides the foundation for promoting high-quality teaching and learning, allowing learners to realize their full potential. Good classroom management is an important factor affecting academic success as it determines levels of learners' engagement and disciplinary behavior. As schools become increasingly diversified, teachers face the increasing need to develop more effective, efficient, and inclusive classroom management practices than ever.

Moreover, classroom management is important in good teaching and significantly influences learners' behavior and academic performance (Batool et al., 2023). The number of practices intending to develop constructive engagement on the part of the learners, decrease undesired conduct, and bring about academic success among learners are collectively considered part of classroom management as the techniques and strategies utilized by the teacher to make an organized learning environment that helps facilitate learning. Studies have repeatedly proven that effective classroom management is directly related to improved academic achievement, positive learners' behavior, and a welcoming and pleasant learning environment (Karasova & Nehyba, 2023).

Furthermore, the research on classroom management is very significant. It creates a structured learning environment for learners both academically and socially. Strategies in effective classroom management help clear expectations and routines that are implemented to reduce undesirable learners' behavior and, therefore are important for positive learners' interaction (Combest, 2021). Also, a classroom management plan has been proven to be possible with small children which reduced the disruptive behavior in a classroom setting and at the same time decreased teachers' stress (Zorowski et al., 2020).

Also, recent researches highlighted various dimensions of classroom management that contribute to effective behavior management. For instance, a systematic review identified vital characteristics of learner-centered communication strategies that effectively reduced behavioral problems while increasing learners' engagement (Horner et al., 2019). Additionally, learners are motivated to participate and demonstrated interest in the subjects while giving prompt feedback that improved their academic performance. The interaction between teachers and learners strengthened the learners' active collaborative learning. Learners

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are benefited greatly from this kind of two-way communication because it encouraged thoughtful discussion in class and enabled teachers to modify their lessons in response to learners' needs, resulted in a dynamic and cooperative learning environment (Qureshi et al., 2023).

On top of that, DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012, commonly known as the DepEd Child Protection Policy, particularly on Positive and Non-Violent Discipline of Children, significantly agrees to highlight a holistic, positive, and proactive approach to teaching that will help children develop appropriate thinking and behavior, which will result in self-discipline. Learners do have fundamental rights. According to the order, positive discipline includes setting long-term goals for development and teaching values and lifelong skills through everyday challenges and circumstances. This study focused on how teachers' classroom management practices correlate with learners' behavior, enabling a positive and productive learning environment.

Thus, this study aimed to address the gap by examining the classroom management practices of teachers in terms of planning, classroom instruction, and evaluation and assessing their relationship with the behavior of learners, particularly in elementary classrooms in Manolo Fortich District IV.

This study was grounded on three theoretical perspectives: Behaviorism, Social Learning Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory. Support for this discussion comes through these theories on which understanding the relationship between the independent variable- teachers' classroom management practices and the dependent variable, which is the learners' behavior; this study was well anchored.

The first theory is Behaviorism by B.F. Skinner, which suggested that environmental stimuli determined the behavior and, therefore that behavior can be changed using reinforcement and punishment. Particular to education, operant conditioning theory by B.F. Skinner is particularly very relevant because it suggested that the teachers can effectively manage their learners' behavior by creating positive reinforcements for desired behavior and consequences for undesired ones. Recent research has reinforced this perspective, indicating that consistent positive reinforcement can improve learners' discipline and engagement (Simonsen & Fairbanks, 2019).

Also, recent study of Ozen and Yildirim (2020) addressed the views of teachers toward classroom management. The study highlighted the challenges and practices experienced through the process. The independent variables included classroom management practices that addressed all techniques, beliefs, and approaches of teachers toward handling the classroom. Dependent variable was the learners' behavior as this was affected by how the teachers manage and relate to the class. It explored how various classroom management practices affect the overall atmosphere in the classroom and how the learners respond.

Additionally, Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory also informed the discussions of this study as it highlighted the significance of observational learning in behavior acquisition. This theory supported with the recent study of Freiberg et al. (2020) has proposed that learners acquire behavior by observing the behavior of their teachers as well as their peers. Hence, effective classroom management practices included modelling desired behavior such as cooperation, conflict resolution, and self-control. The findings of recent studies were the classrooms where the learners have active teachers who modelled desired behavior tend to have relatively fewer disruptive behavior among the learners. This mutual relationship leads to the conclusion that higher teachers' classroom management proficiency relates with better disciplinary learners' behavior.

Finally, the Ecological Systems Theory by Urie Bronfenbrenner then supported by the latest study of Amali et al. (2023) which suggested that individuals are affected by various environmental systems around them. Therefore, this view emphasizes the management practices of teachers to influence the behavior of learners. It places classroom management in the ecological model further discusses how such strategies relate to larger systems such as school policies, peer influences, and family involvement that make up the mesosystem. This means that effective classroom management is not an independent variable but an interactive pattern in a network of interplays that influence the learner development process. Therefore, in this ecological perspective, classroom management is very crucial in determining the behavior of learners within the overall network of effects. On the other hand, harmful influences outside the school environment can hinder the behavioral response of learners to effective classroom management strategies. This study borrowed ideas from Behaviorism, Social Learning Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory to study complex interrelations among variables in a given research location.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive correlational design to investigate the relationship between teachers' classroom management practices and learners' behavior in Manolo Fortich District IV, Division of Bukidnon. It allowed the investigation of the correlation between variables without including their manipulation, a descriptive correlational design was appropriate for this study (Hamaker, 2024). The used method allowed the study to accomplish its objectives of identifying the learners' level of behavior and classroom management practices used by teachers, analyzing the connection between these two variables, and finding any significant correlations or associations.

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In this study, various statistical methods were employed to analyze the data collected from the CMS and the Classroom Behavior Rating Scale. Problem 1 used the Mean and Standard Deviation in determining the teachers' classroom management practices, which consisted of the following: planning, classroom instruction and evaluation. Also, problem 2 used the Mean and Standard Deviation in determining the learners' behavior. Following the descriptive analysis, inferential statistics examined the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Specifically, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was calculated to assess the strength and direction of the relationships between teachers' classroom management practices (as measured by the CMS) and learners' behavior (as measured by the Classroom Behavior Rating Scale) in problem 3. This method was particularly suitable for identifying whether higher proficiency in specific classroom management practices correlates with improved learners' behavior.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. What is the level of teachers' classroom management practices in terms of:

- 1.1. planning;
- 1.2. classroom instruction; and
- 1.3. evaluation?

Table 1: Overall, Teachers' Classroom Management Practices.

Variables	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Planning	4.47	0.57	Good	Highly Evident
Classroom Instruction	4.60	0.52	Excellent	Very Highly Evident
Evaluation	4.49	0.59	Good	Highly Evident
Overall	4.52	0.56	Excellent	Very Highly Evident

Note: 4.50 – 5.00 = Excellent & Very Highly Evident 3.50 – 4.49 = Good & Highly Evident
2.50 – 3.49 = Fair & Evident 1.50 – 2.49 = Poor & Less Evident 1-1.49 = Very Poor & Least Evident

Table 1 shows the overall level of teachers' classroom management practices. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 4.52 with SD = 0.56, described as Excellent and interpreted as Very Highly Evident. This suggests that the teachers' classroom management practices promote an environment of support, efficiency, and motivation for the learning process and in reinforcing positive behaviors in their class. The teachers' classroom practices were planning, classroom instruction, and evaluation. Moreover, good planning forms the basis of effective classroom management as it facilitates teachers to plan specific objectives, organize materials ahead of time, and anticipate potential challenges.

Moreover, teachers create the conditions for smooth learning process by organizing well-planned classes and creating classroom instructions and routines well. Also, the primary objectives of classroom management practices are to maintain the interest of learners, enhance active participation, and create a respectful learning environment where learners show positive disciplinary behavior. Teachers achieve this through resolving disorderly behavior promptly and fairly, facilitating collaborative learning, and implementing effective teaching strategies. Learners are more likely to understand expectations and be motivated to remain focused when they are provided with positive reinforcement and clear communication.

Furthermore, evaluation is an important component to classroom management because it allows teachers to measure learners' intellectual and behavioral growth. Through formative and summative evaluations combined with reflective practice, teachers can identify areas that need improvement and adjust their management strategies accordingly. Teachers ensure that their classroom climate supports both academic success and reinforcing positive disciplinary behavior.

In addition, proper preparation is the basis for effective classroom management according to Kauffman et al. (2021) who wrote that well-planned lessons improve learners' participation and reduce disruptive behavior. The notion that great classroom management practices are evident in a well-disciplined and well-organized learning environment which learners are kept on task and attention is given clear support. Planning effectively allows teachers to anticipate possible difficulties and adopt a problem-solving approach towards ensuring discipline, eventually leading to a more organized, productive learning environment and less disruptive behaviors occurring.

Similarly, Lewis (2020) stressed the importance of active engagement in the classroom instruction upon seeing that interactive teaching strategies significantly minimize class disruptions and enhance on-task behavior. As active participation ensures a harmonious and respectful class environment, this provides support that teachers' management practices are not only self-evident but also very effective. Teachers can reduce the possibility of learners' behavioral issues by employing engaging strategies that create an energetic learning environment in which learners feel invited to join in.

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Meanwhile, the variable, Classroom Instruction, has the highest Mean of 4.60 with SD = 0.52, described as Excellent and interpreted as Very Highly Evident. This implies that an organized and interactive learning environment that certainly reflect good behavior and academic success of the learners are observed as a result of a clear and effective classroom instruction. Teachers establish a high expectation that is highly observable in learners' interest and classroom management when they consistently use engaging strategies, provide immediate feedback, and establish clear procedures throughout the class. This means that investing in instructional management strategies is not only beneficial but also important to develop a learning environment which learners are motivated and reinforced with positive disciplinary behavior.

As Gage et al. (2021) mentioned in their study that good classroom practices—providing prompt feedback, for example, and pertinent response opportunities—are especially associated with the highest level of engagement and with the highest level of compliance in following classroom rules. Learners will be more likely to remain attentive, minimize misbehaviors, and create a positive learning environment when they are given feedback and clear chances to contribute on a regular basis.

Lewis (2020) further attested to this claim by stressing that well-defined classroom instruction results into fewer behavior issues in class. It further indicates how learners are more knowledgeable about what is happening, feel more at ease, and less likely to misbehave when teachers use constant and engaging instruction. Also, it indicates that the ability of a teacher to effectively manage classroom teaching is an important element in producing a disciplined learners.

Conversely, the variable, Planning, got the lowest Mean of 4.47 with SD = 0.57, described as Good and interpreted as Highly Evident. It suggests that even though planning is a highly evident variable of teachers' classroom management practices, possibly there could be some indicators needed to develop to reach the same level as classroom instruction. While still viewed as being good, the slightly lower mean would suggest that the teaching planning practice of teachers can be enhanced through collaboration among co-teachers and school heads in order to adapt different ideas, or improving suitable framework of activities which will later be used to achieve learners' needs.

Collaboration may involve creating inclusive lesson plans that accommodate different learning styles, sharing ideas in handling unexpected disruptions, and opportunities for active engagement. Improving the planning process may also involve creating more accurate learning objectives, such as innovative teaching styles, and ensuring time is utilized efficiently to maximize learning opportunities. Teachers may create a more orderly, responsive, and productive learning environment in the classroom by planning collaboratively with school heads and co-teachers, which will eventually improve learners' behavior and academic achievement.

The same way with Setyaningsih and Suchyadi's (2021) research, it emphasized that planning is the basis of well-organized classroom management since it involves preparing the materials ahead of time and strategies in place to create a supportive learning environment. Even though planning received a little lower rating, it still received a Highly Evident interpretation, indicating that teachers recognize its value and use it carefully, although there may be space for improvement. Moreover, through thorough and deliberate planning, it greatly enhances learners' involvement and academic performance in addition to reinforcing classroom discipline and order. Thus, improving teachers' planning practices through collaboration and professional growth may help classroom management reach even greater heights of efficiency.

Problem 2. What is the learners' level of behavior?

Table 2 shows the learners' level of behavior. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 4.38 with SD = 0.65, described as Most of the Time and interpreted as Generally Positive Behavior. It suggests that most learners demonstrate desirable behaviors, such as following classroom rules, respecting teachers, and engaging in group activities. However, it indicates that these behaviors are not yet fully rooted in all learners since this rating does not reach the Always category. Some learners may consistently exhibit positive behavior, while others may only do so in certain situations or require reminders and reinforcement.

Table 2: Learners' Behavior

<i>Every learner...</i>	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. apologizes when they make mistakes.	4.51	0.58	Always	Consistent Exemplary Behavior
2. avoids arguments with their classmates.	4.17	0.73	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
3. completes tasks and assignments on time.	4.30	0.61	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
4. respects teacher's instructions and guidance.	4.33	0.67	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
5. follows classroom rules without being reminded.	4.36	0.67	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior

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6. feels confident in their ability to succeed in class.	4.39	0.57	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
7. effectively resolves social conflicts when they arise.	4.35	0.71	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
8. actively participates in group activities and lessons.	4.40	0.65	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
9. remains patient when faced with challenges in class.	4.46	0.62	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
10. responds appropriately to normal criticism or teasing.	4.36	0.73	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
11. stays focused in class even when faced with distractions.	4.29	0.68	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
12. tries to solve problems independently before asking for help.	4.47	0.62	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
13. shares materials and resources with their classmates willingly.	4.43	0.65	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
14. listens to their classmates' opinions and ideas during group work.	4.43	0.59	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
15. helps maintain a positive and respectful classroom environment.	4.48	0.61	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior
Overall	4.38	0.65	Most of the Time	Generally Positive Behavior

Note: 4.50 – 5.00 = Consistent Exemplary Behavior
 2.50 – 3.49 = Mixed Level of Behavior
 1.00-1.49 = Significant Lack of Positive Behavior
 3.50 – 4.49 = Generally Positive Behavior
 1.50 – 2.49 = Infrequent Demonstration of Desirable Behavior

Moreover, further reinforcement strategies are necessary to promote consistency so that the classroom environment promotes positive behavior among learners. Also, teachers can help the learners internalize positive behaviors by implementing structured behavior management approaches, positive reinforcement techniques, and social-emotional learning activities. Teachers must encourage peer collaboration, provide clear behavioral expectations, and recognize exemplary conduct to their learners so that it can also help ensure that positive behavior becomes a natural and consistent part of the learning experience.

It brings in line with Duran et al. (2020) that learners' behavior is greatly influenced by the support and involvement of their teachers. It is clear that learners are more likely to exhibit positive disciplinary behavior when they believe their teachers are pleasant and supportive. A single strategy might not be effective for every learner since some might adjust to a supportive setting with ease, others might need extra help and guidance to meet classroom rules. This emphasizes how important it is for teachers to use adaptable and flexible teaching strategies and practices that meet the needs of each unique learner. Clear rules, regular reinforcement, and a well-organized classroom can all help to maximize the benefits of teacher support.

Additionally, addressing differences in learners' behaviors can be facilitated by creating a cooperative and inclusive learning environment. The study emphasizes how crucial relationships between teachers and learners are to uphold discipline and encouraging academic success. Eventually, in order to produce a really positive learning experience, teachers' support—which is an important component in influencing behavior—must be combined with strategies that accommodate diverse learners.

Moreover, indicator 1, *Every learner apologizes when they make mistakes*, has the highest Mean of 4.51 with SD = 0.58, described as Always and interpreted as Consistent Exemplary Behavior. It suggests that the effectiveness of current classroom norms and values in encouraging responsible behavior. It also proposes that learners are open to ethical and social expectations which can be reinforced further through ongoing modeling by teachers. Moreover, this positive behavioral trend can also be used as a basis for enhancing other elements of classroom discipline, including conflict resolution and peer relationships, leading to a more respectful and cooperative learning environment.

In the same manner, Reinke et al. (2021) and Reddy (2019) also emphasized the strength of positive teacher-learner relationships in promoting respect and adherence to classroom rules. Their results are consistent with the present study's suggestion that learners are open to ethical and social standards, which are maintained under the guidance of a teacher. When learners see their teachers as fair and approachable, they are likely to adopt values like respect and responsibility, resulting in a

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disciplined and cooperative classroom. This further supports the findings of the study that teachers' influence and classroom management are significant factors in determining learners' behavioral pattern.

On the other hand, indicator 2, *Every learner avoids arguments with their classmates*, got the lowest Mean of 4.17 with SD = 0.73, described as Most of the Time and interpreted as Generally Positive Behavior. This suggests that learners typically performs constructive interpersonal skills, which promotes a polite and cooperative learning environment. This can be sustained even further through exercises that promote social-emotional learning and conflict resolution techniques, which can maintain and strengthen peaceful peer relationships. Learners can develop closer bonds with their peers by reinforcing positive behaviors through cooperative learning and teacher modeling, which promote teamwork. The classroom environment can become even more welcoming, encouraging, and favorable to learning these social skills are present. Similarly, the research by Cillessen et al. (2021) emphasized how important peer relationships and cooperative learning opportunities are to encourage good social behavior and preserving a peaceful learning environment in the classroom. In their study, they stressed that learners' ability to successfully discuss social circumstances can be strengthened by providing them with organized opportunities for collaboration. This implies that even while learners typically have good interactions with their peers, supervised group activities can help them develop their interpersonal skills even further. Teachers can help learners to create a closer, more respectful bonds with one another by encouraging cooperation and truthful communication.

Moreover, DeRosier et al. (2020) confirmed this view by illustrating that the promotion of collaborative learning environments can enable learners to assist each other academically and socially, thereby lessening conflict and disruptive behavior. Peer relations and the inclusion of conflict resolution techniques in the classroom activities has the potential to lessen the inconsistency witnessed in the ability of learners to keep away from arguments. If learners worked collaboratively and established a harmonious relationship from each other, it will be easier for them to perform tasks and minimize class disruptions and misbehaviors.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' classroom management practices and learners' behavior?

Table 3: Correlation Analysis.

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable	r-value	p-value	Description	Interpretation
Classroom Management Practices					
Planning	Learners' Behavior	0.32	0.03	LPC	Significant
Classroom Instruction		0.51	0.00	MPC	Significant
Evaluation		0.35	0.03	LPC	Significant

Note: Significant when computed p-value <0.05

SPC = Strong Positive Correlation MPC = Moderate Positive Correlation LPC = Low Positive Correlation

Table 3 shows Pearson's correlation test between the teachers' level of classroom management practices and learners' behavior. Only one independent variable in teachers' classroom management practices show a moderate positive correlation, which is the classroom instruction. It shows a computed r -value of 0.51 with p -value=0.00, describes with moderate positive correlation and is significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that the quality, strategies, and effectiveness of classroom instruction have a direct relationship on how learners behave in the classroom. Also, better discipline, focus, and general positive behavior in learners can result from teaching that is well-organized, interesting, and effectively controlled. Additionally, a well-disciplined learning environment is facilitated by structured and engaging teaching approaches, as demonstrated by the study of Duran et al. (2020) which emphasized the significant relationship between classroom instruction and learners' behavior. Learners are more likely to stay attentive, participate actively, and follow classroom rules when they believe their teachers are supportive and pleasing. According to the study, teaching strategies applied in class reduce disruptive behavior while nurturing a good learning environment. In addition to improving academic achievement, effective teaching promotes a respectful interactions and adherence to classroom rules.

On the other hand, the variables Planning and Evaluation show low positive correlation towards learners' behavior. It presents a computed r -value of 0.35 with p -value=0.03 with the description of low positive correlation in terms of evaluation and reveals a computed r -value of 0.32 with p -value= 0.03. Both evaluation and planning are interpreted as significant at 0.05 level of significance. This means that evaluation plays an important role in influencing learners' behavior. Daily evaluations encourage learners to take greater responsibility for their learning since ongoing feedback helps them identify their areas of strength and growth, which lessens their possibility for misbehaviors.

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Additionally, continuous evaluation helps teachers modify their methods to better meet the requirements of their learners which will create a supportive learning environment that rewards participation and discipline. It is in line with Hidayat et al. (2024), who stressed that evaluation is an important component in encouraging responsibility, discipline, and a well-organized classroom environment in addition to being a tool for evaluating academic achievement.

Furthermore, planning is essential to influencing how learners behave in class. Teachers establish a motivating and orderly class environment that promotes good discipline when they thoughtfully plan classes that integrate a variety of instructional strategies. Learners may concentrate on studying rather than misbehaving when a session is well-planned because it reduces distractions. The same way with Ahn et al. (2021), who discovered that teachers who put in the effort to organize lessons and implement different teaching techniques create a supportive learning environment in the classroom, which eventually improves learners' discipline.

As can be seen from the same table, all three independent variables are significant at 0.05. In summary, taking it at the coefficient level, these teachers' level of classroom management is correlated to the learners' behavior, with a p -value less than 0.05. Thus, the correlation analysis yielded that the null hypothesis test (H_0) was rejected. With the following findings, moderate and low positive correlations.

Likewise, this suggests that teachers' classroom management practices correlates in shaping learners' behavior. It specifically illustrates how planning, classroom instruction, and evaluation all play an important role in shaping learners involvement and discipline in class. Teachers can develop an organized classroom conducive to positive behavior by applying correct planning to their sessions. In addition, dynamic and engaging teaching significantly influences classroom environment and learners' engagement. The implication from this study is that a more organized and active learning environment can be created by using effective teaching strategies. Also, the preservation of learners' motivation and positive behavior is supported by fair and established evaluation processes. In light of everything, teachers should enact complete classroom management practices that involve thoughtful planning, smooth classroom instruction, and just evaluation to raise positive disciplinary behavior of learners.

Similarly, Batool et al. (2023) posited that effective classroom management is a central element that controls learners' behavior that surpasses mere responsibility to maintain orderliness. Based on their study, learners are motivated to develop self-control, sense of responsibility, and genuine learning enthusiasm when their teachers purposefully apply strategies intended to support active learning engagement, lessen disruptive behavior, and ensure a welcoming and inclusive classroom environment. By taking a full approach to classroom management, teachers can successfully manage misbehavior and enable learners to become responsible for their own learning by meeting both instructional and behavioral needs.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings mentioned above, this study has come up with the following conclusions:

1. Teachers believe in being capable of delivering an interactive, systematic, and organized classroom instruction. They provide learners' active participation and reflect positive behavior effectively.
2. Learners frequently comply with classroom expectations and rules.
3. Teachers' classroom management practices are relevant in molding learners' behavior in class.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions, this study come up with the following recommendations to likely sustain the teachers' classroom management practices concerning the learners' behavior.

1. Teachers may continue to uphold interactive class discussions and use of diverse instructional strategies. Also, school heads may continuously support teachers' collaboration by emphasizing in the collaborative expertise or Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions about topics which will sustain classroom instruction and further enhance teachers' planning, and appropriate evaluation practices.
2. School heads, teachers, parents, and learners must work together to support and maintain positive learners' behavior. Teachers may keep using positive reinforcement techniques like verbal praise, incentive schemes, and recognition initiatives to inspire learners.
3. By establishing clear expectations and promoting school standards, school heads, teachers, and parents can encourage positive conduct among learners.

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